

Low percolation threshold of polypropylene-specially designed graphene nanocomposites

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Aim of the project

Graphene properties

- Mechanical
- Electrical
- Barrier
- Thermal

Graphene related materials used as fillers

- Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs > 10ML)
- Few-layers graphene (FLG 2-10 ML)
- Graphene oxide (GO)
- Reduced graphene oxide (r-GO)

Different properties!

Processing problems:

- Agglomerates easily
- High percolation thresholds
- Low compatibility with polymers

Goal: industrially-relevant, simple process

Matrix **Fillers**

Batch melt mixing
Brabender Type: W50
10min, 50RPM

Instrumentation:

- Hot Disk thermal analyser
- DSC
- TGA
- Electrical conductivity measurement setup

Filler: specially designed graphene

Compression moulding

3 - 5 layers

Morphology

Thermal properties

Electrical conductivity

Polymer	Filler type	Method	Percolation Threshold [wt. %]	Reference
PP	SDG	Melt mixing	~1	This work
	Graphene Platelets		9	Li J. Et al. 2007
	Expanded Graphite		8-12	Pionteck J. 2015
	Graphene Platelets		8-6	Zhang J. 2017
	Graphene Platelets		8	Strååt, M. 2011
	Graphene Platelets		12	Kalaitzidou K. 2007
	Graphene Platelets		8-12	Li Y. 2011

Conclusions:

- In this work, we have presented an industrially relevant melt-mixed system of polypropylene and specially designed graphene.
- Due to its unique structure, the filler has the potential to create a three-dimensional extended structure, thus allowing for a very efficient dispersion.
- The dispersion efficiency can be seen via the excessively low electrical percolation threshold observed by this study.
- The influence of graphene on thermal properties has been also investigated.

Acknowledgments:

References:

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- Röding, M., Gaska, K., Kádár, R., Lorén, N. (2017) *ACS Applied Nano Materials* 1(1), 160-167